

THE EFFECTS OF COUPLE STRESS AND SURFACE ROUGHNESS IN SQUEEZE FILM LUBRICATION OF SPHERICAL BEARINGS

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Abstract

In this paper, a theoretical study of combined effects of surface roughness and couple stresses on squeeze film lubrication of spherical bearings is analyzed. The modified Reynolds Equations accounting for the couple stresses and surface roughness using Deterministic Theory are mathematically derived. It is applied to study the effects of roughness and couple stresses in spherical bearings. In order to get the expression for pressure the modified Reynolds equation is solved. Then by making use of this expression we obtain the expressions for load carrying capacity, which in turn is used to find the expression for response time. These expressions are numerically computed and the results are presented graphically. From the numerical computations of the results, it is found that, the effect of couple stresses is to increase the load carrying capacity. A parameter characteristics different type of roughness is identified. It is observed that in case of transverse roughness pattern the load capacity increases where as it decreases for longitudinal roughness pattern.

Keywords: *Couple stress fluids, Surface roughness, Load capacity and Squeezing time.*

Nomenclature:

c	Clearance width in journal bearing or spherical bearing
h_n	Nominal film thickness
h_s	Mean height of roughness asperities
h	Total film thickness
h_f	Final film thickness
h_i	Initial film thickness
\dot{h}	Squeeze term
k	Ratio of the viscosities near the surface to the purely hydrodynamic zone
l	Couple stress parameter
e	Eccentricity
ε	Eccentricity ratio
μ	Viscosity of the base lubricant
ϕ	Roughness parameter
η	Material coefficient of the couple stress fluid

x, y, z	Cartesian coordinates
\underline{p}	Hydrodynamic pressure
\overline{p}	Dimensionless hydrodynamic pressure
\underline{W}	Load carrying capacity
\overline{W}	Dimensionless Load carrying capacity
\underline{t}	Squeeze time
\overline{t}	Dimensional squeezing time
V	Squeeze velocity

1. Introduction

Hydrodynamically lubricated spherical bearings are widely used in a variety of applications involving severe operating conditions of speeds, loads; etc. It is observed fact that the fluids containing additives or contaminants enhance the lubrication process. These additives have a desirable effect of enhancement of viscosity and a consequent rise in load capacity. Usually, these additives are in the form of long chain organic compounds. In recent years experimental studies [Oliver (1988), Spikes (1994)] have shown clear evidence of load enhancement and friction reduction effects due to the pressure of additives. Therefore the effects of additives on the fluid rheology of a lubricant received great research attention. Since the flow behavior of a Newtonian lubricant blended with various additives could not be described accurately by the classical continuum theory many micro continuum theories have been proposed [Ramanaiah (1979), Airman et al (1973), Stokes (1966)]. Among these theories the Stokes theory [16] is the simplest theory that accounts for the effects of couple stresses, body couple and asymmetric tensors. An inverse solution for finite journal bearing lubricated with couple stress fluids by [Elshakawy and Guedouar (2001)] and a theoretical study of squeeze film behavior for a finite journal bearing lubricated with couple stress by [Lin (1998)] are investigated.

In general the bearing surfaces are rough in nature. When the film thickness between the surfaces is very small, the surface asperities begin to interact with the lubricant. Then the effect of surface roughness must be taken into account to study the behavior of lubrication systems, where the flow takes place in narrow recesses. The term squeeze film applies to the phenomenon of two lubricated surfaces approaching each other with a normal velocity. The thin film of lubricant contained between these two surfaces acts as a cushion which prevents the surface configuration fluid properties and applied load among other things, a certain time is required to squeeze out the lubricant. In general the relation between the load carrying capacity and the rate of approach of the two lubricated surfaces is studied in most squeeze film analysis. The characteristics of squeeze film bearings were studied by [Pan et al. (1966)]. Squeeze film between rotating annuli was investigated by [Allen and Mckillop (1970)]. [Shukla (1978)] gave a new deterministic theory to study the effects of the asperities is of the same order of magnitude as the minimum film thickness. [Rodkiew et al. (1987)] applied this method to study the effects of surface roughness on EHD film. The surface roughness effects on the pure squeeze film behavior of a long partial journal bearing operating under a time-depending oscillating load are analyzed by [Lin et al. (2002)]. [Hsiu- Lu Chiang et al. (2004)] studied the lubrication performance of finite journal bearings considering effects of couple stresses and surface roughnesses. Moreover, [Naduvanamani et al. (2005)] examine the effect of surface roughness on the squeeze characteristics of couple stress lubricant between a sphere and a flat. [Chu et al. (2010)] made an elastohydrodynamic lubrication analysis for different squeeze action geometries, with special attention to sphere-flat plate case, considering the combined effects of surface roughness and couple stress fluids.

This paper considers the combined effects of couple stress and surface roughness upon the performance of spherical bearings. The mean film pressure is obtained by integrating the Reynolds equation and then the bearing characteristics can be calculated immediately.

2. Basic Equations

The one-dimensional form of the generalized Reynolds equation for rough surfaces is [11], the film thickness h is written in terms of nominal film thickness, h_n and mean height asperities h_s corresponding to the rough surfaces.

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial x} \left(F \frac{\partial p}{\partial x} \right) = U \frac{d}{dx} (h_n + 2h_s) + \dot{h} \tag{1}$$

Where,

$$F = \frac{M - \text{Tanh}(M)}{M^3} \frac{(2h_s)^3}{2k\mu} + \frac{1}{4} \left[(h_n - 2h_s) + 2h_s \frac{\text{Tanh}(M)}{M} \right]^2 \frac{4h_s}{k\mu(2M)} + \frac{1}{12\mu} \left[(h_n - 2h_s)^3 - 12l^2(h_n - 2h_s) + 24l^3 \text{Tanh} \left(\frac{h_n - 2h_s}{2l} \right) \right]$$

$$M = \alpha h_s, \quad \alpha = \sqrt{\frac{1}{k\phi}}, \quad l = \left(\frac{\eta}{\mu} \right)^{\frac{1}{2}}$$

Consider squeezing between two eccentric spherical surfaces of radii r_1 and r_2 which are approaching each other with a velocity V as shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Squeezing film in spherical bearing

The nominal film thickness h_n is given by

$$h_n = c(1 - \epsilon \cos \theta)$$

where $c = R_1 - r_1$ is the clearance width and $\epsilon = \frac{e}{c}$ is the eccentric ratio.

The flow flux in this case is obtained by

$$Q = \frac{F}{r} \frac{dp}{d\theta} 2\pi r_1 \sin \theta \tag{2}$$

$$F = \frac{M - \text{Tanh}M}{M^3} \frac{(2h_s)^3}{2k\mu} + \frac{1}{4} \left[4h_s \frac{\text{Tanh}(2M)}{K\mu(2M)} \right] \left[(c(1 - \epsilon \cos \theta) - 2h_s) + 2h_s \frac{\text{Tanh}(M)}{M} \right]^2$$

Where,

$$+ \frac{1}{12\mu} \left[[c(1 - \epsilon \cos \theta) - 2h_s]^3 - 12l^2 [c(1 - \epsilon \cos \theta) - 2h_s] + 24l^3 \text{Tanh} \left[\frac{c(1 - \epsilon \cos \theta) - 2h_s}{2l} \right] \right] \tag{3}$$

$$M = \alpha h_s, \quad \alpha = \sqrt{\frac{1}{K\phi}}, \quad l = \left(\frac{\eta}{\mu} \right)^{\frac{1}{2}}$$

The flux Q obtained from the equation of continuity is

$$Q = 2\pi r_1^2 V \sin^2 \theta \tag{4}$$

From equations (2) and (4), we obtain

$$\frac{dp}{d\theta} = \frac{Vr_1^2 \sin\theta}{F} \tag{5}$$

The boundary condition for equation (5) is

$$p = 0 \quad \text{at } \theta = \frac{\pi}{2}$$

Integrating equation (5) and using the above condition, we get the expression for pressure distribution as

$$p(\theta) = \int_{\theta}^{\frac{\pi}{2}} \frac{r_1^2 V \sin\theta}{F} d\theta \tag{6}$$

The load capacity W is given by

$$W = 2\pi r_1^2 \int_0^{\frac{\pi}{2}} p \sin\theta \cos\theta d\theta \tag{7}$$

Using equation (6) and equation (7) we get the load capacity as

$$W = 2\pi r_1^4 V \int_0^{\frac{\pi}{2}} \frac{\sin^3\theta}{F} d\theta \tag{8}$$

and squeezing time, t for the surfaces to approach from the initial eccentric position ($\mathcal{E} = 0$) to a final eccentric position \mathcal{E} is given by

$$t = \frac{2\pi r_1^4}{W} \int_0^{\mathcal{E}} \int_0^{\frac{\pi}{2}} \frac{\sin^3\theta}{F} d\theta d\mathcal{E} \tag{9}$$

Where F is given by equation (3)

The non dimensional load capacity is given by

$$\begin{aligned} \bar{W} &= \frac{Wc^2}{\pi r_1^4 \mu} \\ \bar{W} &= 24V \int_0^{\frac{\pi}{2}} \frac{\sin^3\theta}{\bar{F}} d\theta \end{aligned} \tag{10}$$

and the non dimensional squeeze time is given by

$$\begin{aligned} \bar{t} &= \frac{tWc^2}{24\mu\pi r_1^4} \\ \bar{t} &= \int_0^{\mathcal{E}} \int_0^{\frac{\pi}{2}} \frac{\sin^3\theta}{\bar{F}} d\theta d\mathcal{E} \end{aligned} \tag{11}$$

where,

$$\bar{F} = 6 \frac{M - \text{Tanh}(M)}{kM^3} (2\bar{h}_s)^3 + 6(2\bar{h}_s) \frac{\text{Tanh}(2M)}{k(2M)} \left[\left((1 - \varepsilon \cos \theta) - 2\bar{h}_s \right) + 2\bar{h}_s \frac{\text{Tanh}(M)}{M} \right]^2 + \left(1 - \varepsilon \cos \theta - 2\bar{h}_s \right)^3 - 12\bar{l}^2 \left(1 - \varepsilon \cos \theta - 2\bar{h}_s \right) + 24\bar{l}^3 \text{Tanh} \left[\frac{\left(1 - \varepsilon \cos \theta - 2\bar{h}_s \right)}{2\bar{l}} \right]$$

Equations (10) and (11) are analyzed numerically and graphs have been plotted.

3. Results and Discussions

Load carrying capacity:

In Fig. 2 and 3 the load carrying capacity of spherical bearing \bar{W} plotted with \bar{h}_s , the mean height of roughness asperities for various values of couple stress parameter \bar{l} . As the mean height of roughness asperities \bar{h}_s increases, the load capacity \bar{W} increases with the increase of couple stress parameter \bar{l} . It is observed from these graphs that the mean height of roughness asperities \bar{h}_s increases, the load capacity \bar{W} increases for low values of $\bar{\phi}$ and the roughness parameter decreases for high values of $\bar{\phi}$. The lower values of $\bar{\phi}$ may represent the case of transversal roughness where as the higher values of $\bar{\phi}$ may correspond to longitudinal roughness.

It is seen from the Fig. 4 the load capacity increases for $k > 1$ as \bar{h}_s increase when there is no roughness and decreases for $k < 1$ i.e., the load capacity increases as the thickness of the peripheral layer increases when the peripheral layer viscosity more than the middle layer viscosity.

In Fig. 5 the load capacity, \bar{W} plotted against \bar{h}_s , the mean height of surface asperities for various values of rough parameters $\bar{\phi}$. It is observed from these graphs, that the load capacity \bar{W} increases as the mean height of surface asperities \bar{h}_s increases for low values of $\bar{\phi}$ i.e., transversal roughness and the load capacity decreases as \bar{h}_s increases for high values of $\bar{\phi}$ i.e., longitudinal roughness.

In Fig. 6 the load capacity, \bar{W} plotted against the couple stress parameter \bar{l} , for various k , it is the ratio of peripheral viscosity near the surface to the viscosity in the middle of the lubricant. As \bar{l} increases, the load capacity \bar{W} increases with the increase of k .

Squeezing time:

In Fig.7 and 8 the squeezing time of spherical bearing \bar{t} plotted with \bar{h}_s , the mean height of roughness asperities for various values of couple stress parameter \bar{l} . As the mean height of roughness asperities \bar{h}_s increases, the squeezing time \bar{t} increases with the increase of couple stress parameter \bar{l} . It is observed from these graphs that the mean height of roughness asperities \bar{h}_s increases, the squeezing time \bar{t} increases for low values of $\bar{\phi}$ and the roughness parameter decreases for high values of $\bar{\phi}$. The lower values of $\bar{\phi}$ may represent the case of transversal roughness where as the higher values of $\bar{\phi}$ may correspond to longitudinal roughness.

In Fig. 9 the squeezing time, \bar{t} plotted against \bar{h}_s , the mean height of surface asperities for various values of rough parameters $\bar{\phi}$. It is observed from these graphs, that the squeezing time \bar{t} increases as the mean height of

surface asperities \bar{h}_s increases for low values of $\bar{\phi}$ i.e., transversal roughness and the squeezing time \bar{t} decreases as \bar{h}_s increases for high values of $\bar{\phi}$ i.e., longitudinal roughness.

In Fig.10 the squeezing time, \bar{t} plotted against the couple stress parameter \bar{l} , for various k , it is the ratio of peripheral viscosity near the surface to the viscosity in the middle of the lubricant. As \bar{l} increases, the squeezing time \bar{t} increases with the increase of k .

Fig. 2 : Variation of \bar{W} with \bar{h}_s for various values of \bar{l}

Fig. 3 : Variation of \bar{W} with \bar{h}_s for various values of \bar{l}

Fig. 4: Variation of \bar{W} with \bar{h}_s for various values of \bar{l}

Fig. 5: Variation of \bar{W} with \bar{h}_s for various values of $\bar{\phi}$

Fig. 6: Variation of \bar{W} with \bar{l} for various values of k

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Fig. 7: Variation of \bar{t} with \bar{h}_s for various values of \bar{l}

Fig. 8 : Variation of \bar{t} with \bar{h}_s for various values of \bar{l}

Fig. 9 : Variation of \bar{t} with \bar{h}_s for various values of $\bar{\phi}$

Fig. 10: Variation of \bar{t} with \bar{l} for various values of k

4. Conclusions

In this paper the generalized Reynolds equation with additives and surface roughness is applied to squeeze films between Spherical bearings.

It is concluded that as the mean height of roughness asperities increases, the load capacity and squeeze time increases with low values of $\bar{\phi}$ i.e., transversal roughness and decreases with high values of $\bar{\phi}$ i.e., longitudinal roughness. Also the load capacity and squeezing time increases when the couple stress parameter increases.

5. References

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